
COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

23rd

ANNUAL REPORT

1979

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Acknowledgements

The scholar at his book-wheel is a reproduction of an engraving in Agostino Ramelli's *Le diverse et artificiose machine. . .*, Paris: 1588. It first appeared in the Council's third annual report, which explained that "the picture symbolizes the interest of the Council on Library Resources in both the content of books and the mechanics of library service." The engraving has appeared in each annual report since that time.

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Contents

- 4** **Members of the Council and of the Board of Directors**
 - 5** **Council Committees and Officers**
 - 5** **Council Staff**
 - 7** **The Year 1978–1979 and the Future**
 - 13** **Program Highlights**
 - 30** **Publications Resulting from CLR-Supported Programs
and Fellowships**
 - 33** **CLR-Supported Projects Active in Fiscal 1979**
 - 39** **Schedule of Appropriations for Council-Administered
Projects**
 - 40** **Opinion of Independent Accountants and Financial
Statements**
 - 48** **Index**
- Program Guidelines (inside back cover)**

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Members of the
Board of Directors**

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Nancy E. Gwinn, *Program Officer*⁵
Jacqueline G. Jackson, *Secretary and Receptionist*
C. Lee Jones, *Program Officer*⁶
Paul B. Lagueux, *Information Systems Specialist*

1. Mr. Kempner was elected to succeed Dr. Davis at the November 1978 annual meeting.

2. Elected at the November 1978 annual meeting.

3. Until August 15, 1978.

4. As of June 18, 1979.

5. Formerly Information and Publications Officer, Ms. Gwinn became Program Officer on January 23, 1979.

6. As of November 1, 1978.

Nadine S. Leavitt, *Secretary*⁷
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Leone I. Newkirk, *Program Associate*⁹
George A. Parsons, *Information Systems
Specialist*
Carl M. Spaulding, *Program Officer*¹⁰
James L. Tew, *Accountant*

7. Until September 29, 1978.

8. As of November 29, 1978.

9. Until her retirement, June 30, 1979.

10. Until January 19, 1979.

The Year 1978–1979 and The Future

The Council on Library Resources both funds and undertakes activities that hold promise of solving some of the generic problems of libraries and the interests of those they serve. Support for Council operations and programs is provided by a number of foundations, including, for fiscal year 1979, the following: the Carnegie Corporation of New York, the Commonwealth Fund, the Exxon Education Foundation, the Ford Foundation, the William and Flora Hewlett Foundation, the Lilly Endowment, Inc., the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, the Rockefeller Foundation, the Alfred P. Sloan Foundation, and the National Endowment for the Humanities.

The Council and its supporters together are one element in a large set of organizations and activities concerned with the production, distribution, and use of recorded information. The Library of Congress, the National Library of Medicine, the National Commission on Libraries and Information Science, other federal libraries and agencies, library organizations, some scholarly groups and publishers, to say nothing of other libraries and many individuals, are all, like the Council, involved to one extent or another in what has quite suddenly become a lively arena.

The Council's special concern is with academic and research libraries because they are a fundamental component of the entire system. The content of their comprehensive collections, taken together, is an essential part of the foundation of our civilization; their staffs of distinctively trained subject bibliographers, information

specialists, and administrators contribute in significant ways to the work of scholars and the performance of libraries of all kinds.

The record of grants made during 1978–1979 and an account of activity in Council-administered projects constitute the bulk of this report. As in past years, fellowships and internships have been awarded, support has continued for a few programs designed to improve library services and management, modest assistance has been provided for efforts related to standards development and collection preservation, and the extensive activity of recent years in automation and bibliographic services has been substantially supplemented with additional funds and increased staff effort.

In short, the work of the Council and those it assists goes on. Many librarians have had a chance to expand their professional horizons. The understanding of effective managerial techniques and their application is more widespread in large libraries than it was a few years ago. Recognition of the seriousness of the problem of paper deterioration is more prevalent. Standards that are essential to the application of computers to bibliographic operations have been set. Useful bibliographic products have been produced, and some CLR-funded development work, especially in the area of computer applications, has begun to thrive in operating situations. The details of these and other programs are described in the chapter “Program Highlights.”

What Lies Ahead?

Over the centuries since the invention of printing, an established and, on balance, remarkable set of institutions and procedures has evolved into the contemporary general research library. But in the last ten or fifteen years, the exponential rise in publication and the increase in available bibliographic information, coupled with dwindling fiscal resources, have sown the seeds of revolution, and it will take nothing short of a revolution of sorts to permit libraries in the future to meet service obligations, to contribute in reasonable ways to national informational objectives, and to live within the bounds of their own finite financial resources.

As the participants inevitably learn, however, revolutions are mixed blessings, in large part because change breeds confusion. Libraries seem to be no exception. Excessively competitive attitudes slow progress. Redundant efforts tax limited financial and intellectual resources. Access to bibliographic and substantive information is occasionally impeded rather than eased, and technology is at times misapplied. These and other signs do not necessarily suggest

that there are fundamental flaws in the methods being used to make changes. They reflect, rather, the complexity and magnitude of the task of accommodating the imperatives of a revolution to organizations that have relied traditionally on the evolutionary process. Further, while the high level of activity indicates a period of dynamic change, the corresponding sense of direction one would expect has appeared, until recently, to be missing.

However, to the careful observer there are now visible some signs that a sense of direction really does exist. The confusion of the present stems in large part from the fact that the heading itself is not yet widely perceived and many markers are still lacking. The limited resources of CLR are dedicated, at this point in time, to participation in the task of refining the map to the future, to supporting at least some of the work required to move libraries along these new paths, and to improving understanding of the long-range implications and effects of the library revolution. Periodically we remind ourselves of the ends that prompt this substantial expenditure of time and money. For us, as for our many partners, the objectives are still centered on the effective preservation and use of recorded information; the provision of library services essential to research, teaching, and learning; and the development of appropriate links to scholarly bodies and the world of publishing, both inseparably bound to libraries in the system of scholarly communication.

What lies ahead? Clearly, some substantial changes in the ways libraries work and in the ways they are used. The expectations of users and expansive programs projected by an enthusiastic and maturing library profession are confronted by rising costs and powerful competition for limited funds. While articulate and persuasive arguments for more support are made, their success cannot be assured. In fact, measured only in terms of the possibility of economic relief, future prospects are, on their face, bleak. Sensing this predicament, librarians have turned elsewhere for help. Computer and communications technology, or more accurately the capabilities of that technology, has for some time been promoted as a kind of life preserver for floundering libraries. But like many such devices, the end effect is governed as much by the accuracy with which it is deployed as by its intrinsic buoyancy.

The skill with which technology is put to use is a matter of great importance. Even after years of experience, it is not certain that prospects and problems are wholly understood. On the one hand, an emphasis on automating traditional procedures and activities still persists without establishing whether or not the characteristics of the technology itself might actually eliminate or at least change

some of those procedures in fundamental ways. The economic benefits of automation seem likely to be marginal at best if managers aspire to substitute rather than to transform.

The other and even less well understood aspect of this technology is the manner in which it will be used to store, process, and transmit information of importance to scholars, research workers, and students. This matter is the essence of the real library revolution that is, whether we like it or not, now well under way. It will transform and add to the substance of library resources and services and will ultimately change and make more intimate the relationships among libraries and between libraries and many other enterprises to which libraries are functionally related. The fact of change is inevitable. The influence of librarians (and those who would see libraries flourish) on the character of that change cannot be both great and accidental.

In light of the dilemmas posed by rising costs, reduced resources, and technological complications, it is not surprising that librarians have for some time been turning their attention to methods of library management. The doctrine of self-sufficiency has, as a result, come under close scrutiny. It appears now that the concept hasn't really been rejected, but rather that it has been redefined.

In the past, self-sufficiency was measured by the range and depth of the collection. Numbers of volumes provided evidence of past success, and rates of growth continuing security. Today the goal is still self-sufficiency, but it is a state to be reached by a variety of programmatic means rather than by collecting activity alone. In essence, libraries are in the process of finding their place in a broader context and of developing new ways to meet old objectives. It is important that they succeed; if they fail, the options are either a substantial role reduction or pervasive performance degradation.

What is actually happening to give credence to the earlier assertion that there is, in fact, a developing sense of direction? The combination of professional aspirations, user expectations, fiscal constraints, technical capabilities, and growing managerial sophistication is promoting change of many kinds. Of special importance are the trends in two fundamental areas, bibliographic structure and collection control. It seems certain that these changes will affect not only the research library world, but the nature of research itself.

Basic bibliographic structure, for both library users and library procedures, used to begin and end with each library's card catalog. The collections represented by the catalog—whether large or small, fragmentary or comprehensive, mundane or distinguished—have been, for users, the point of beginning and, almost always, of ending

as well. Now, bibliographic structure is becoming library independent. The change started in specific scientific areas and is moving to other disciplines. While local resources retain the merit of proximity, they—and the catalog that is the guide to them—are increasingly inadequate as a foundation for research. As a result, extensive data bases are being developed, initially as a resource for processing by libraries but ultimately as a guide to all recorded information. This prospect gives every library a demanding new responsibility—new at least in practice if not in principle—of providing its users with their personal windows into the expanded bibliographic world.

Not only is the underlying bibliographic structure changing; the nature of the local catalog itself also needs review. With the advent of on-line bibliographic data bases, scholars and researchers have discovered many new ways of searching for information, ways that far exceed the routes imagined by those still tied to the format of catalog cards, even though that format might have been transferred to the cathode ray tube. Interdisciplinary studies remind us that topics and subjects are no longer bound by arbitrary rules based on outmoded theories of the categorization of knowledge. Even the logic of maintaining a “definitive” record for each item in nondefinitive collections is open to question.

But the catalog of any given library will still have a critical role. While its importance as a bibliographic tool may decrease, and aside from its function as an internal location device, the catalog is likely to become a key management tool in the second area of concern, i.e. collection control. Far-reaching changes are needed in acquisition, retention, preservation, and even storage policies to take into account new patterns of use, regional affiliations, and the evolving prospect of national collections. Library managers, as well as users, may find that the form of the catalog and its records must be changed to meet these evolving managerial requirements.

Library collections need to be seen more as an aggregation of discrete parts than as a homogenized accumulation, and collection control policies need to be related specifically to those parts. The acquisition, processing, and maintenance of materials generate the bulk of library operating costs. Those costs are best contained and justified by concentrating on collections themselves, rather than on the attendant processes.

As the collections and bibliographic systems in each library change in the context of network-provided services and products, as the number and kinds of data bases expand and complement published materials, and as the path between each initial request for an item and its fulfillment becomes more complex, library participation in

the research process itself will become more extensive and demanding. In the end, it is the ability of the people who assume responsibility for library performance and who are accountable in the eyes of those who depend on libraries that must balance the economic, organizational, and technological factors in the equation for future success.

“Utopia” by anyone’s definition will not come easily. Information has become a big and profitable business, and research library goals and the means chosen to accomplish them are at times in conflict with the objectives of others. Long-term aspirations of universities and the needs of scholarship need to be kept firmly in mind. The public interest case to extend access to recorded information worldwide, at acceptable costs, and without constraint, must be pressed with skill and conviction by all who feel concern.

Put simply, there is now some sense of where we are going—getting there is the task facing CLR and the many others enlisted in the same cause.

Program Highlights

To help identify problems that appear to be most pressing, the Council periodically poses certain key questions. How can a national bibliographic structure be built so that anyone requiring information can identify and locate what is required with reasonable ease and at an acceptable cost? How can the management and internal operations of libraries be improved so that the library patron can make efficient use of collections and human resources? How can the nation's library collections be preserved as a national resource and yet made widely available? What is needed in terms of professional education and training for academic and research librarians and library managers? What is the role of the academic library in higher education and how can that partnership be enhanced? What kinds of basic information and analysis do we need about library economics, library relationships to other components of the information community, library staffing and collections, etc., that will help libraries improve their performance in support of research and instruction?

While the answers to such questions may be uncertain, the simple process of asking them helps to identify problem categories needing attention. Certain of these topics become focal points of CLR program concerns, which presently include: bibliographic services, library resources and their preservation, library operations and services, professional education and training, and research and analysis. The following pages discuss Council activity for the 1979 fiscal year (July 1, 1978, to June 30, 1979) in the context of these five concerns.

Bibliographic Services

A significant portion of Council activity has been devoted throughout the years to improving the means by which libraries and their users learn about what has been published, then locate and acquire desired items. Programs in this area have been national and international in scope. Through support of the judicious application of computer techniques to library processes, of cooperative cataloging programs, and of the development of standards, the Council has sought ways to help libraries reduce unit costs of repetitive operations while improving library services. At the same time, the Council has encouraged the development of nationwide services that will help all libraries and has fostered the establishment of major components of an emerging national library and information system.

Bibliographic Service Development Program

The principal event of the 1979 fiscal year was the beginning, in November 1978, of CLR's Bibliographic Service Development Program (BSDP). The program works toward the provision of effective bibliographic services that will meet the existing and future needs of scholarship and research, toward the improvement of bibliographic products, and toward the purposeful control of costs of bibliographic processes in individual libraries. Seven private foundations and the National Endowment for the Humanities are providing funds exceeding \$5,000,000 to support the CLR venture, which is projected to last at least five years.

CLR staff spent the first eight months of program activity identifying and bringing together the parties likely to be most concerned with bibliographic services, reviewing the literature and relevant activities of the recent past, and determining the most fruitful areas for the application of limited resources. Oversight for the effort is provided by a Management Committee, composed of Warren J. Haas, CLR President; William J. Welsh, Deputy Librarian of Congress; and Frederick H. Burkhardt, Past Chairman of the National Commission on Libraries and Information Science and Past President of the American Council of Learned Societies. A Program Committee aids CLR staff in determining courses of action and monitoring projects. Members of this group include Henriette Avram, Library of Congress; Carol Ishimoto, Harvard University; Frederick Kilgour, OCLC, Inc.; Edward Shaw, Research Libraries Group; and Roderick Swartz, Washington Library Network. In addition, BSDP program goals and concerns have been discussed by the Library of Congress's Network

Advisory Committee, whose members, drawn from many information-related organizations, act as liaisons to their associations and represent organizational viewpoints.

From this crucible of discussion and study has been drawn a framework of action, which initially will concentrate on the creation of a bibliographic record service. Issues for consideration include database generation and control, communication between data bases, and promulgation of standards to facilitate information exchange. The BSDP planners are also turning their attention to the problems of individual libraries and their potential capacity to use the products of a nationwide bibliographic record service.

A variety of mechanisms are being used to develop suitable projects that hold promise of advancing BSDP goals. Grants will be given and contracts issued. Ad hoc committees and working groups will be appointed to focus on specific topics. Meetings and conferences will be held to allow for mutual investigation of problems and possible solutions. A broad spectrum of individuals, organizations, institutions, and agencies are being asked to contribute their knowledge and skills to the growing number of tasks necessary to the creation of the nationwide service.

Four grants or contracts were approved prior to June 30, 1979. One consultant reviewed the problems involved in linking bibliographic networks and prepared a request for proposal (RFP) that will result in a detailed assessment of the consequences and requirements of various linking and service options. A second consultant was employed to review the status of work toward establishing standard formats for institutional identification codes and bibliographic holdings notation. Travel grants will allow two U.S. librarians to represent U.S. interests abroad. One will participate in work to develop an international authority system and the other on the promulgation of an International Standard Bibliographic Description for analytic entries. Both efforts are coordinated by the International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions.

An example of an ad hoc committee is the Joint Committee on Bibliographic Standards, composed of technical experts from the major bibliographic utilities, research libraries, the Library of Congress (LC), the National Library of Medicine, and CLR. At its first meeting in June 1979, the group embarked on an effort to assist in the selection of options provided under the new *Anglo-American Cataloging Rules*, second edition, for the machine-based bibliographic utility services in the U.S.

Another working group composed of institutional representatives, staff members of LC's Network Development Office (NDO), CLR staff,

and several consultants held an intensive three-day meeting in May 1979 to review the nationwide data-base design project under way at the Network Development Office. They reviewed the research tasks, some of which have been completed, identified by NDO as necessary in the process of designing a nationwide bibliographic data base. The group verified that the NDO approach was appropriate and rational and suggested some additional activities that would strengthen the project and its results.

Committee for the Coordination of National Bibliographic Control

Jointly sponsored by CLR, the National Science Foundation (NSF), and the National Commission on Libraries and Information Science (NCLIS), the Committee for the Coordination of National Bibliographic Control was established in 1974 to identify and conduct certain activities that would lay the foundation for an improved national bibliographic system. The committee, whose six members represent the library, publishing, abstracting and indexing, information dissemination, and allied communities, sponsored a workshop in October 1978 on issues surrounding methods for providing subject access to information. The resulting report and its recommendations for action were disseminated widely to library schools and major library and information organizations and were submitted to the Educational Resources Information Center (ERIC).¹ The National Endowment for the Humanities also provided funds for the workshop.

At the time the committee was established, there was little purposeful planning at the national level toward developing a comprehensive system of bibliographic control. Because more formal mechanisms have since emerged, the committee determined that its activities should be terminated and that further meetings as a separate entity were unnecessary.

American National Standards Committee Z39

The American National Standards Committee Z39 (ANSC Z39) is one of several subject matter committees reporting to the American National Standards Institute, a national clearinghouse and coordinating agency for voluntary standards in the United States. ANSC Z39 is responsible for the development of standards relevant to information systems, products, and services as they relate to libraries, information services, and publishing. Further, Z39 is responsible for encouraging use of its standards in library, publishing, document

delivery, information dissemination, and information and data handling systems.

CLR has supported ANSC Z39 since 1961. This past year two successive one-year grants to the committee's secretariat, the Council of National Library and Information Associations, Inc., brought the total CLR authorization for the committee to over \$216,000. NSF, NCLIS and OCLC, Inc. have also provided support. The committee is currently seeking funds for its continuing program through contributions from member and nonmember organizations and federal agencies.

CONSER/COM

In September CLR awarded a grant of \$23,000 to the National Library of Canada (NLC) to enable NLC to publish, in computer output microfiche (COM), bibliographic records produced in the CONSER (Conversion of Serials) project. The CONSER project is a cooperative file-building effort initiated five years ago to develop a national data base of serials records. CLR funded and managed the project using the resources of 14 North American libraries and the on-line computer facilities of OCLC, Inc, which has now assumed the management role. Production of CONSER/COM allows libraries that are not members of OCLC to have access to all the authenticated records in the CONSER file. As of June 30, 1979, NLC had received 93 subscriptions from 13 countries including Canada. In the United States, the Library of Congress will begin distribution of CONSER microfiche early in the new fiscal year. As an additional service, the Library is taking steps to make the entire machine-readable file of CONSER records available on tape at nominal cost. The file will be issued annually and will contain all CONSER records, whether authenticated or not.

Although CLR is no longer responsible for CONSER management, the Council still has active interest in the project, particularly as it relates to the overall development of national bibliographic control. In conjunction with the U.S. Office of Education (USOE), CLR has taken the initiative to organize meetings of CONSER participants and USOE grant recipients, whose projects involve retrospective conversion of union lists of serials to machine-readable form. The grants were made under Title II-C of the Higher Education Act. The anticipated result of the meetings is the assurance that these discrete projects are more closely coordinated and compatible with the development of the national data base of serials records. This work is being carried out under the guidelines of the Council's Bibliographic

Service Development Program, one element of which is national data-base construction.

Non-Roman Alphabet at OCLC

CLR has joined with other funding agencies in supporting a program at OCLC to provide libraries with the capability for automated cataloging of materials in non-Roman alphabets. Since libraries currently catalog non-Roman materials manually, having such a capability will, it is hoped, improve access to such materials and help ameliorate processing costs. The work will be done in concert with the Library of Congress and others to ensure maximum usefulness to the library community as a whole.

Data-Processing Handbook

The first edition of Joseph Becker's and Robert M. Hayes' CLR-supported *Handbook of Data Processing for Libraries* was published in 1970. Royalties from this edition were used for a second edition, which appeared in 1974 and sold over 4,000 copies. In August 1978 Mr. Hayes received another CLR grant, which will make possible the preparation of a third, completely revised, edition. Emphasis in the new edition will be on an analysis of the actual experience of libraries in the development, evaluation, installation, and operation of computer-based systems. As in the past, the work will be published by John Wiley & Sons, Inc., and the Council will accumulate royalties to be used either for another edition or for related work.

Universal Bibliographic Control

If the Bibliographic Service Development Program is successful, a scenario such as this might develop: A library user in any public, academic, special, or school library, large or small, sits down at a computer terminal and within a few minutes locates several books and journal articles that bear directly on his or her current interest. The records through which the user sifts would have been generated in a variety of ways by a large number of agencies. Ideally, each record would have been generated only once and then shared by all who needed it. Library users would thereby have access to records of nearly all of the publishing output of the nation.

If this concept of access, whether through machine-readable or manual means, is carried forward by other countries, then each nation will have established bibliographic control over its own publications and, if suitable standards are used, can share the resulting

records with other nations. This concept is the basis of the program of the International Office for Universal Bibliographic Control (UBC), administered by the International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA). The Council has supported this office, which is located within the British Library, since its establishment in 1974.

One of the UBC office's major activities is the promulgation, publication, and monitoring of use of the numerous International Standard Bibliographic Descriptions (ISBD). New descriptions currently in preparation include rules for preparing records of antiquarian materials, printed music, and analytics (i.e., journal articles, chapters in books, etc.). Acceptance of the ISBD's as standards will ensure uniformity in bibliographic records and facilitate their exchange across national boundaries. The office also acts as a secretariat to working groups and individuals engaged in special international bibliographic projects, collects and disseminates information relating to bibliographic standards, coordinates meetings of national and international cataloging and bibliographic organizations, and edits and issues a variety of publications on standards and other bibliographic matters. In addition to CLR support, the office receives income in the form of contributions from national library and cultural agencies, sales of publications, and UNESCO contracts.

Library Operations and Services

Over the years the Council has supported a number of projects devoted to helping libraries operate more efficiently and serve their constituencies more effectively. The Council has approached this area of its program in a variety of ways. A series of grants, for example, have gone to academic libraries for experimental programs involving joint planning by library and teaching faculty of ways to integrate the library more closely with the educational process. Another group of programs has focused on improving library management. Support has also been given to other associations that are in turn attempting to assist member libraries to improve the conduct of their daily business. Management, operations, and services are so closely inter-related that it is impossible to assist in one area without affecting others. They are parts of a continuum that must be seen as a whole.

Academic Library Program

The central effort of the past year is the Academic Library Program administered by the Office of Management Studies (OMS) of the Association of Research Libraries (ARL). CLR (drawing on funds from

the Carnegie Corporation), the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, the Lilly Endowment, and ARL itself have joined in support of the project. The OMS has been funded by the Council since 1970 and has applied a kind of self-help methodology to library operations through such programs as the Management Review and Analysis Program, the Academic Library Development Program, and the Collection Analysis Project. These programs provide guidance to academic libraries in the form of manuals, procedures, and personal consultation to help the libraries examine themselves, analyze their operations, identify strengths and weaknesses, and outline areas and methods for change.

All academic libraries in the United States are eligible to participate in the Academic Library Program. A modest fiscal commitment, estimated at \$4,000-\$7,000, is required to participate. A Planning Project for Small Libraries, supported by the Lilly Endowment, will allow six libraries in Indiana to begin self-studies in the fall of 1979. On the drawing board are a services development program, a community and two-year college study, and a preservation module.

The five-year project will be advanced by the training of up to 100 librarians as consultants to assist libraries in conducting their self-investigations. During the year the ALP Advisory Committee, on which a CLR staff member participates, established procedures for the selection of the first consultant-trainees. Applicants were sought in early 1979 for the first Consultation Skills Workshop to be held in October. As of May 31, 251 applications had been received, and regional interviews were scheduled for the month of August. OMS plans to train about 20 persons each year.

Final Awards Under College Library Program

In the fall of 1978, the final awards to be made under the College Library Program, jointly sponsored by CLR and the National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH), were announced. The three awards bring to 35 the number of institutions that have participated in the program since its genesis in 1969. Each institution has designed activities to enhance the library's role in the educational process. Teaching faculty, administrators, librarians, and, in some cases, students have assisted in the formulation of each project. The institutions are required to share in program costs by providing at least 25 percent of the total budget from funds over and above the regular library budget.

Two of the institutions, Lake Forest College in Illinois and Tusculum College in Tennessee, will expand instructional programs

begun with grants from CLR's Library Service Enhancement Program (no longer operating). A required sophomore humanities course is the foundation of the Tusculum program, while Lake Forest will use computerized data bases as primary instructional tools. The third grantee, Franklin and Marshall College in Pennsylvania, plans to implement a comprehensive library instruction program in support of eight areas of the curriculum in the humanities and historical studies.

As announced at the close of fiscal 1978, CLR and NEH have decided to discontinue the College Library Program and no new applications will be accepted. It is planned that the new Academic Library Program (see above) will, in its services development module, incorporate the experience and expertise of persons who have participated in the College Library Program.

IFLA's Professional Programs

The Council has awarded a new grant of \$75,000 to the International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA) to enable the organization to develop further its professional programs. The grant is the fourth CLR award to IFLA for the work of its general secretariat. Total CLR support since 1971 amounts to \$439,000.

IFLA's expansion of its professional activities began in 1976 following a restructuring of the association. The revised statutes created a professional organization composed of divisions by type of library, by library activity, and by region. Within the divisions are 35 sections and round tables that engage the energies of school, public, special, academic, and national librarians from 106 countries.

To coordinate the programs and projects of the diverse groups, IFLA created a professional board and hired a deputy secretary-general. In addition to acting as secretary to the professional board and coordinating divisional and sectional programs, the deputy secretary-general has worked in recent months to expand IFLA's links with the Arab world and with French- and English-speaking Africa. The deputy will also act as secretary to a new program management committee, which will direct and coordinate the work of IFLA's programs for universal bibliographic control, universal availability of publications, and international MARC. Formation of the new committee was approved by the IFLA Executive Board in May 1979; it will become effective on September 1.

IFLA has had consultative status with UNESCO for many years and has provided an important international forum for the discussion

of library problems. In addition to Council funding, IFLA receives income from membership dues, sales of publications, conference proceeds, UNESCO grants and contracts, the Dutch government, and the Canadian International Development Agency.

Microform Service Development

The past fiscal year brought to a close a CLR grant to Princeton University as part of Princeton's Microform Service Development Program. Grants from the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation and the Xerox Corporation were used to replace worn equipment, improve the microforms facilities, reduce cataloging arrearages and complete analytical cataloging of microform sets. The CLR grant, awarded in July 1976, was used to support training of division staff, improve graphics, develop an orientation program for other library staff and students, and hold a regional seminar for microforms librarians from other libraries. The project's final report pointed to an increase in the use of the Microform Division in 1977-78. Over 15,800 persons had used over 44,000 items.

Library Resources and Their Preservation

As inflation has eaten away the purchasing power of library budgets, the need to preserve the resources at hand has become even more critical. The cost of replacements, whenever available, are high, and prices of new materials are constantly rising. Even the most self-sufficient libraries are beginning to listen to the lyrics of resource-sharing tunes sung with increasing frequency by their less-well-off neighbors. More purposeful collection building combined with a well-planned preservation program appears to be the theme song of the future.

Preservation has always been high on the list of Council priorities, even though CLR has not been able to support preservation programs or collection development at individual libraries. A December 1976 National Preservation Program Planning Conference, called by the Library of Congress and supported with a CLR grant, identified a variety of needs that were recently reiterated by Pamela Darling: "professional training of conservators and continuing education for librarians; . . . model organizational approaches; . . . discovery of safe 'minor repairs' to be performed by nonconservators; . . . expanded cooperative programs for the sharing of scarce expertise; . . . development of an ethic or philosophy to relate technical operations responsibly to the 'value' of materials; . . . effective and economical

mass treatment of deteriorated materials."² Ms. Darling's comments introduced a series of articles that explored these and other issues in an attempt to focus attention and provide factual data on aspects of the preservation problem.

Collection building is equally important; numerous questions require an analytic approach. Assessing the concept of "national collections," understanding better the relationship between proximity of materials and their use, and improving methods for assessing collection strength are only a few of the issues of importance that must be addressed. Specific action to be taken in the future is not yet certain, but the past year has seen some progress. A small step was taken when a CLR grant was awarded to support a summer 1979 conference of book selection officers from academic libraries to discuss the problem of retrospective collection development.

National Periodicals Center

Last year's report described the preparation by Council staff of the 256-page *A National Periodicals Center Technical Development Plan* (Washington, D.C.: Council on Library Resources, 1978). Although the Council's official role in this effort was concluded when the report was turned over to the Library of Congress early in the present report year, CLR staff received numerous requests to explain the intent of the plan and its meaning to library users, scholars, the business information community, publishers, and other concerned citizens. Program staff therefore prepared a slide show illustrating the concept of an NPC. The show was presented at meetings and conferences sponsored by library and information organizations around the country.

A number of scholarly and educational organizations have endorsed the concept of a National Periodicals Center. As this report year closed, the National Commission on Libraries and Information Science's Advisory Committee on a National Periodicals System had commissioned a group broadly representative of interested constituencies to prepare draft legislation.

Preservation and Paper

CLR and the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation invited about twenty individuals with knowledge of paper manufacturing, publishing, and library book preservation programs to contribute to a May 14, 1979, discussion in New York. The participants sought to gather information about book paper and its use and to identify ways to address prospective aspects of the collection preservation problem.

The meeting agenda focused on current practices in the manufacture of paper and its use for books and journals. Examples of questions raised were: Is book paper that meets reasonable specifications for permanence and durability readily available in sufficient variety and at acceptable cost? If appropriate paper is available, why is it not more generally or universally used for publication of books and journals? If it is not available, or if other obstacles exist, what action is required, and by whom?

At the conclusion of the discussion, those present encouraged the continued pursuit of issues identified and formed a committee, under the direction of Herbert S. Bailey, Jr., of the Princeton University Press. The committee will propose procedures for identifying preservation objectives and options for action, recommend ways to arrive at acceptable standards, and attempt to extend understanding and wider recognition of the preservation problem itself. CLR has set aside a small sum to support the activities of the committee.³

National Shelflist Measurement Project

The University of California, Berkeley, has published a compilation of statistical data on the holdings of 27 research libraries, including the Library of Congress. The report's preparation was supported by a CLR grant awarded in January 1978. Entitled "Titles Classified by the Library of Congress Classification: National Shelflist Count," the 64-page report represents the third phase in a study of the distribution of holdings among research libraries that was undertaken by the Chief Collection Development Officers of Large Research Libraries. The project director believes that the project "provides the beginnings of a national program for the evaluation and coordination of research library collections."⁴

An Experiment with "Books for College Libraries"

In 1977, CLR provided a small grant to Stockton State College in Pomona, New Jersey, to experiment with the machine-readable tapes used to produce the second edition of *Books for College Libraries*. CLR had assisted the preparation of both first and second editions of the work. The second edition, published in 1975 by the American Library Association (ALA), is a catalog of the 40,000 basic titles any four-year liberal arts college should have in its library if it intends to provide students with an adequate education.

Stockton maintains a machine-readable listing of its own collection. The college used the ALA tapes to compare its holdings and

generate lists that could be used for evaluation, for purchasing, and for circulation studies. To encourage other small libraries that lack sophisticated programming staff, Stockton successfully employed an information sciences student to prepare the programs. Stockton used the services of the New Jersey Educational Computing Network to complete the project.

Professional Education and Training

How can academic libraries attract the highly qualified people needed to carry out the libraries' missions of service to scholarship and teaching? More important, how can academic libraries retain competent staff and build in them the skills necessary to provide, with their peers, leadership in higher education management? And even more fundamental, how can the profession as a whole recruit the most well-qualified individuals to its ranks and keep them there? The Council has sought to provide some answers in terms of programs that provide for staff development and focus on increasing the knowledge and skills of professional library staff members. Three programs were active in this fiscal year and are described below. But the conviction persists that the broader topic of basic professional education for academic and research libraries needs more concentrated attention.

Academic Library Management Intern Program

As in former years, the Council selected skilled and able individuals to participate in its Academic Library Management Intern Program. The program is designed to create a pool of highly qualified library managers who will be capable of moving into senior administrative slots as these become vacant in future years. For the 1979-80 academic year, two women were chosen, each to work with the director and top administrative staff of one of the country's important academic libraries selected for its recognized administrative excellence. Each intern receives a stipend equal to her normal salary and benefits (up to \$25,000). **Rebecca D. Dixon**, director of the Library Services Division of the Center for the Study of Youth Development, Boys Town, Nebraska, will intern with Jay K. Lucker, director of libraries at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT), while **Susan K. Nutter**, associate head of the Engineering Libraries at MIT, will intern with James F. Govan, director of the University of North Carolina library.

Following a review of the program, it was determined that the

period of internship would be reduced to ten months for the 1980–81 academic year. Council advisors agreed that the shortened period would not significantly dilute the experience and would free funds for additional internships. Up to five interns will be chosen for the seventh year of the program.

Although no guarantees can be made in terms of career advancement, former interns now hold such responsible positions as university librarian at Canada's McMaster University, director of the J. Hugh Jackson Business Library at Stanford, assistant librarian for general reader services at Princeton, and director of the central library at the Vanderbilt University Libraries in Nashville.

Health Sciences Library Management Intern Program

Like its predecessor above, the Health Sciences Library Management Intern Program is designed to increase the number of librarians who, in addition to having the intellect, personality, and character required for director-level positions, also have a firm grounding in management processes and techniques. The program is funded by the National Library of Medicine and administered by the Council.

Three women emerged successfully from a field of 19 applicants for the 1979–80 academic year. **June E. Bandemer**, assistant director of the Falk Library of the Health Professions, University of Pittsburgh, will intern with C. K. Huang, director of the Health Sciences Library, State University of New York at Buffalo. **Eleanor Goodchild**, director of library services at the Los Angeles County Harbor General Hospital, will work with Richard A. Lyders, executive director of the Houston Academy of Medicine, Texas Medical Center Library. Finally, **Leonor S. Ingraham**, coordinator of collection development and head of public services at the Health Sciences Library, University of Oregon, will intern with Gerald S. Oppenheimer, director of the University of Washington Health Sciences Library.

Health Sciences Interns receive stipends (up to \$25,000) that cover their basic salary and benefits. In addition to working with the director of a major academic health sciences library, interns spend two weeks at the National Library of Medicine.

CLR Fellowship Program

The oldest of the Council's professional development programs, the CLR Fellowship Program, was suspended following the selection of ten fellows for the 1979–80 academic year. In the eleven years of

the program, 215 fellowships have been awarded. Thus far, CLR Fellows have produced nearly 80 journal articles and at least 15 books and occasional papers. Some fellows have used the opportunity to improve their technical and administrative skills through short-term internships or work experiences. Others have shared their research in conference programs or applied their new skills to the improvement of their current work situations. It should be noted that, while the annual awards program has been suspended, the Council continues to entertain research proposals from individuals throughout the year.

The recipients of the awards and their projects in the final round of the CLR Fellowship Program follow.

Judith S. Braunagel, assistant professor, SUNY at Buffalo Library School, and **Rao Aluri**, research assistant, OCLC, Inc. To compile a guide to U.S. government scientific and technical information sources.

Boyd Childress, periodicals librarian, Western Kentucky University. To study the history and development of the libraries of the eight state universities in the South from 1860 to 1880 in order to determine their relationship to parent institutions.

Sheila D. Creth, assistant director, University of Connecticut Library. To investigate current approaches and methodologies in the area of manpower planning and job analysis as reflected in selected academic libraries and private industry.

George S. Grossman, director of the Law Library, University of Minnesota. To study the historical development of legal literature and legal research tools in England.

William E. Hannaford, Jr., acquisitions librarian, Middlebury College. To study collection development in ten small college libraries.

Mary E. Pensyl, head, NASIC Search Service, Massachusetts Institute of Technology. To study the impact of user demands on the reference departments of academic and research libraries that have offered online bibliographic services for several years.

Anne B. Pitternick, professor, School of Librarianship, University of British Columbia. To investigate sources of support for bibliographic activities in the United States with emphasis on public and private funding and the economics of publishing.

Patricia Ann Polansky, Russian bibliographer, University of Hawaii. To work for three months at the Scott Polar Research Institute in Cambridge, England, and to attend the 14th Pacific Science Congress.

Suzanne Striedteck, chief, Serials Department, Pennsylvania State University. To study the effectiveness of technical services operations from the point of view of general reference librarians.

Research and Analysis

In 1956, the first major CLR project involved a sequence of studies aimed at developing "targets for research in library work." A series of 18 studies evolved under the direction of Ralph R. Shaw, and the resulting multi-volume set was published by Rutgers University under the title *The State of the Library Art*. The project developed under the guidance of a group of experts that included not only librarians but also "library-problem-minded persons drawn from natural science, scientific instrumentation and business-machine work."⁵

Council interest in sponsoring research has not waned in the intervening years. But it has been a long time since CLR has defined a structured, formal approach. An organized program of research would, of course, touch on all areas of Council interest, such as bibliographic control, collection development, and library management. It might well be broader in focus, looking at the heart of information processes, at how society uses information, and how the transfer of information can be most effectively accomplished for the general good. It might well be narrower, taking a creative approach to specific library processes, to defining the relationships between libraries, publishers, jobbers, indexers, and other sectors of the information community.

In the past year, the Council has discussed these ideas with a number of consultants and interested persons. Although a definite program in this area has yet to be organized, CLR has responded to research proposals on an individual basis and will continue this practice in the future.

New Edition of "British Library Resources"

Robert B. Downs, Dean of Library Administration Emeritus, University of Illinois, will prepare a second edition of his *British Library Resources* with the aid of a small CLR grant awarded this year. The first edition, published in 1974 by the American Library Association and Mansell of London, has nearly sold out in Britain. Dr. Downs will use the grant to travel to Britain in the fall of 1979 and plans to complete the manuscript in mid-1980.

Academic Library Leaders

The Council has awarded a grant of \$10,000 to Wayne A. Wiegand, assistant professor in the College of Library Science, University of Kentucky, to edit a series of essays to be entitled "Leaders in American Academic Librarianship, 1925-1975." Such well-known figures as William Dix, Keyes Metcalf, Robert Vosper, Louis Round Wilson, and Herman Fussler will be among the twelve to fifteen influential academic librarians to be included. Some of the essays will be published in future issues of *The Journal of Academic Librarianship* prior to their collective appearance as a monograph.

Future Role of Public Libraries

In 1976 and again in 1977, CLR awarded funds to the National Citizens Emergency Committee to Save Our Public Libraries for research activities in preparation for the White House Conference on Libraries and Information Services. A series of background papers were prepared and the first, *Career and Employment Information Services*, was received by the Council in April. In addition, on behalf of the committee Doubleday published a 189-page volume entitled *For the People: Fighting for Public Libraries* (New York, 1979). In the words of the preface, the volume "seeks to help citizens understand how the public library got to be what it is today, the vital role the public library plays in the life of the nation, and how it can assist in the nation's future growth and prosperity."

1. Committee for the Coordination of National Bibliographic Control, "The Subject Access Problem—Opportunities for Solution," mimeographed (Washington, D.C.: Council on Library Resources, 1978).

2. Pamela W. Darling, "Towards a Nationwide Preservation Program," *Library Journal* 104(1979): 1012.

3. For a summary of the meeting, see *CLR Recent Developments* 7(August 1979): 2-3.

4. LeRoy D. Ortopan, *Titles Classified by the Library of Congress Classification: National Shelflist Count*, 1977 ed. (Berkeley: University of California, 1979), p. vii.

5. Council on Library Resources, *1st Annual Report for the Period Ending June 30, 1957* (Washington, D.C.: Council on Library Resources, 1957), p. 19.

Publications Resulting from CLR-Supported Programs and Fellowships 1978-1979

Part 1: Programs

- Anglo-American Cataloging Rules*. 2d ed. Chicago: American Library Association, 1978.
- Association of Research Libraries. Office of Management Studies. Systems and Procedures Exchange Center. *Spec Flyers and Kits*:
- No. 46. Planning for the Future of the Card Catalog.
 - No. 47. Automated Cataloging.
 - No. 48. External Fund-Raising.
 - No. 49. The Use of Annual Reports.
 - No. 50. Fringe Benefits in ARL Libraries.
 - No. 51. Professional Development.
 - No. 52. Cost Studies and Fiscal Planning.
 - No. 53. Performance Appraisal.
 - No. 54. Internal Communication: Library-Wide Policies and Procedures.
- Washington, D.C.: Association of Research Libraries, 1978-79.
- Bruntjen, Scott. "Source Documents for American Bibliography: Three McMurtrie Manuals." *Occasional Paper* 18(1978). Halifax, Nova Scotia: Dalhousie University, School of Library Service. Product of the New England Academic Librarians' Writing Seminar.
- Career and Employment Information Services; How Public Libraries Can Provide an Essential Community Service*. New York: National Citizens Emergency Committee to Save Our Public Libraries, 1979.
- Committee for the Coordination of National Bibliographic Control. "The Subject Access Problem—Opportunities for Solution." Mimeographed. Washington, D.C., Council on Library Resources, 1978.
- "Course-related Library Instruction." *Newsletter of the English Department* 6(October 1978): 1-2. Published by Ball State University, Muncie, Indiana 47306. Describes a project developed under CLR-NEH College Library Program award.
- "Course-related Library Instruction Program: A Three-Way Involvement of Librarians, Faculty, and Students." *Featuring Faculty at Ball State University* 2(October 1978): 1-2. Describes project developed under CLR-NEH College Library Program award.
- Dale, Sheila. "The Adult Independent Learning Project: Work with Adult Self-Directed Learners in Public Libraries." *Journal of Librarianship* 2(April 1979): 83-106. An examination of the program carried out from 1972-76 by the Office of Library Independent Study and Guidance Projects of the College Entrance Examination Board, which was partially funded by the Council.
- Daniels, Westwell R. "An Alternative to Library School." *Library Journal* 103(September 15, 1978): 1702-3.

- Product of the New England Academic Librarians' Writing Seminar.
- Danton, J. Periam, and Pulis, Jane F. *Index to Festschriften in Librarianship 1967-1975*. Munich: K. G. Saur, 1979.
- Darling, Pamela. "National Planning for Preservation in the United States." *Restaurator* 2(1978): 205-13.
- Dodson, Suzanne Cates. *Microform Research Collections: A Guide*. Westport, Conn.: Microform Review, 1978.
- _____. "Toward Bibliographic Control: The Development of a Guide to Microform Research Collections." *Microform Review* 7(1978): 203-12.
- Frick, Elizabeth. "Some of My Best Friends Are Faculty." *Colorado Libraries* 4(June 1978): 7-9. Describes project developed under CLR Library Service Enhancement Program grant.
- Gwinn, Nancy E. "The Faculty-Library Connection." *Change* 10(September 1978): 19-21. Describes projects developed through CLR-NEH College Library Program and CLR Library Service Enhancement Program.
- _____. "A National Periodicals Center: Articulating the Dream." *Library Journal* 103(November 1, 1978): 2166-69.
- International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions. *Anonymous Classics: A List of Uniform Headings for European Literature*. London: IFLA International Office for UBC, 1978.
- _____. *ISBD(M): International Standard Bibliographic Description for Monographic Publications*. London, IFLA International Office for UBC, 1978.
- Morein, P. Grady. "Assisted Self-Study: A Tool for Improving Library Effectiveness." *Catholic Library World* 50(May-June 1979): 422-25.
- A National Periodicals Center Technical Development Plan*. Washington, D.C.: Council on Library Resources, 1978.
- "On Our Minds. . . New England Academic Librarians' Writing Seminar," a series of brief commentaries written by seminar participants. All have appeared in the *Journal of Academic Librarianship*: Bruntjen, Scott. "Librarians in a Time of Uncertainty." (July 1978) Gunning, Kathleen. "Increasing the Reference Librarian's Participation in the Research Process." (September 1978) Mathews, William D. "A Siege of Committees." (November 1978) Sherby, Louise S. "Academic Librarian: Librarian or Faculty Member." (November 1978) Stevens, Norman D. "A Hard Look at Reserve." (May 1978)
- Ortopan, LeRoy. *Titles Classified by the Library of Congress Classification: A National Shelflist Count*. 1977 ed. Berkeley: University of California, 1979.
- Paulson, Peter, et al. "Development and Coordination of Library Services to State Government." *Library Trends* 27(Fall 1978): 165-73.
- Seymour, Whitney North, Jr. *For the People: Fighting for Public Libraries*. New York: Doubleday, 1979.
- Stevens, Norman D. "The Writings of Paul S. Dunkin: A Review Article." *Library Resources and Technical Services* 22(Fall 1978): 349-60.

Product of the New England Academic Librarians' Writing Seminar.

Part 2: Fellowships

Baatz, Wilmer H. "Collection Development in 19 Libraries of the Association of Research Libraries." In *Library Acquisitions: Practice and Theory*, vol. 2. Elmsford, N.Y.: Pergamon Press, 1978.

Bailey, Martha. "Requirements for Middle Managerial Positions." *Special Libraries* 69(September 1978): 323-31.

Benne, Mae. "Educational and Recreational Services of the Public Library for Children." *Library Quarterly* 48(1978): 499-510.

Bowden, Virginia M. "Comparative Analysis of Health Science Libraries' Monograph Collections by Computer." In *The Information Age in Perspective: Proceedings of the ASIS Annual Meeting, 1978*. New York: Knowledge Industry Publications, 1978.

Byrum, John D., Jr. and D. Whitney Coe. "AACR as Applied by Research Libraries for Serials Cataloging." *Library Resources and Technical Services* 23(Spring 1979): 139-46.

Chan, Lois Mai. *Library of Congress*

Subject Headings: Principles and Applications. Littleton, Colo.: Libraries Unlimited, 1978.

McClellan, William M. "Judging Music Libraries." *College and Research Libraries* 39(July 1978): 281-86.

Pinkett, Harold T. "Accessioning Public Records: Anglo-American Practices and Possible Improvements." *American Archivist* 41(October 1978): 413-21.

Smith, Barbara E. "British Depository Arrangements for Official Publications." *Government Publications Review* 4(1977): 123-36.

———. "British Official Publications—I. Scope and Substance." *Government Publications Review* 4(1977): 201-7.

———. "British Official Publications—II. Publication and Distribution." *Government Publications Review* 5(1978): 1-12.

Totten, Herman L. "A Survey and Evaluation of Minority Programs in Selected Graduate Library Schools." *Journal of Education for Librarianship* 18(Summer 1977): 18-34.

Wong, William Sheh. "Alfred Kaimung Chiu and Chinese American Librarianship." *College and Research Libraries* 39(September 1978): 384-88.

CLR-Supported Projects Active in Fiscal 1979 (unaudited)

	Unpaid 6/30/78	FY 1979		Unpaid 6/30/79
		Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	
American Association of Law Libraries, Chicago, Ill.				
Survey of U.S. and Canadian law library resources (\$20,000—1968)	\$ 2,000	\$ -0-	\$ 1,000	\$ 1,000
American Library Association, Chicago, Ill.				
Ethnic and sexual composition/ salary survey for librarians (\$13,856—1977)	11,856	-0-	4,928	6,928
Secretariat for the U.S. National Committee for the UNESCO General Information Program (USNC/UNESCO-PGI) (\$2,500—1978)	2,500	-0-	765	1,735
Association of Research Libraries, Washington, D.C.				
Academic Library Program (\$326,500—1978)	326,500	-0-	58,500	268,000
Office of Management Studies (\$81,136—1974; \$210,000—1975)	23,000	-0-	23,000	-0-
Bibliotheque Royale Albert I^{er}, Brussels.				
Preparation of Belgian exhibit (\$2,000—1978)	2,000	(2,000)	-0-	-0-
Council-Administered Projects				
Academic Library Development Program				
Carnegie-Mellon University (\$21,000—1977)	3,000	(1,266)	1,734	-0-
Drew University (\$18,845—1977)	3,645	-0-	3,645	-0-
North Carolina Central University; for project coordinator (\$73,527—1977)	7,957	(6,096)	1,861	-0-
Seattle University (\$15,510—1978)	10,760	-0-	9,500	1,260

	Unpaid 6/30/78	FY 1979		Unpaid 6/30/79
		Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	
University of Wisconsin- Parkside (\$21,350—1977)	\$ 12,350	\$ (1,270)	\$ 11,080	\$ -0-
Academic Library Management Intern Program (\$100,000—1974; \$265,000—1975; \$110,000—1976)	14,811	234 (59)	14,986	-0-
1978-79 (\$80,000—1977)	65,000	-0-	62,349	2,651
1979-80 (\$95,000—1978)	-0-	58,000	-0-	58,000
Advanced Study Program for Librarians (\$115,000—1975; \$112,000—1976)	11,009	(9,979)	1,030	-0-
Bibliographic Service Develop- ment Program				
Preparation of request for proposal on analyzing the linking of bibliographic utilities	-0-	6,434	434	6,000
Position paper on standards	-0-	2,500	-0-	2,500
Travel grant for U.S. repre- sentative at meeting in Copenhagen on international authority system	-0-	1,105	-0-	1,105
Partial support for U.S. repre- sentative at ISBD(AN) meeting in Sweden	-0-	579	-0-	579
CONSER project (\$250,000—1975)	42,773	(35,223)	7,550	-0-
Fellowship Program (\$644,534—through 1978)	30,240	868 (4,870)	19,325 (11)	6,924
1979-80	-0-	23,569	2,230	21,339
Health Sciences Library Management Intern program				
1978-79	-0-	83,751	62,599	21,152
1979-80		86,730	-0-	86,730
Library Service Enhancement Program (\$220,000—1976; \$194,857—1977)	42,752	(16,363)	26,567 (1,920)	1,742

	Unpaid 6/30/78	FY 1979		Unpaid 6/30/79
		Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	
Council of National Library & Information Associations, Inc. Haverford, Pa.				
Continued support of the American National Standards Committee Z39 Through September 1979	\$ -0-	\$ 20,000	\$ 20,000	\$ -0-
Through September 1980	-0-	30,000	-0-	30,000
Robert B. Downs, Urbana, Ill.				
Preparation of second edition of <i>British Library Resources</i>	-0-	3,000	-0-	3,000
Earlham College, Richmond, Ind.				
Periodical list for <i>Choice</i> (\$7,500—1975)	4,200	-0-	1,000	3,200
Eastern Michigan University, Ypsilanti, Mich.				
Project LOEX (\$41,969—1975; \$4,765—1977)	1,265	(298)	967	-0-
International Council on Archives, Washington, D.C.				
ICA Secretariat (\$72,000—1975)	6,000	(2,230)	3,770	-0-
International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions, The Hague, Netherlands.				
Professional activities of the Secretariat (\$174,000—1975)				
Through February 1979	45,014	(14)	45,000	-0-
Through February 1981	-0-	75,000	9,000	66,000
International Office for Universal Bibliographic Control (\$70,000—1974; \$144,200—1975; \$150,000—1977)	121,756	-0-	50,000	71,756
Iowa State University, Ames, Iowa.				
Mechanized indexing procedures applied to production of subject- enhanced keyword index (\$1,926—1977)	426	-0-	-0-	426

	Unpaid 6/30/78	FY 1979		Unpaid 6/30/79
		Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	
Library of Congress, Washington, D.C.				
COMARC project (\$106,132—1975)	\$ 21,483	\$ (8,983)	\$ 12,500	\$ -0-
Meeting on MARC format for AACR 2 (\$5,843—1978)	5,843	805	4,632	2,016
National Preservation Program, meetings of Ad Hoc Advisory Committee (\$5,960—1977)	4,819	(4,819)	-0-	-0-
Use of the ISSN by the U.S. Postal Service (\$14,231—1978)	8,231	-0-	8,231	-0-
MIDLNET, Green Bay, Wis.				
Toward salary of a technical advisor (\$22,778—1977)	17,778	-0-	-0-	17,778
National Association of State Universities and Land Grant Colleges, Office for Advancement of Public Negro Colleges, Atlanta, Ga.				
Status report on libraries of black public colleges (\$4,000—1978)	1,000	-0-	-0-	1,000
National Endowment for the Humanities, Washington, D.C.				
Continuation of College Library Program (matching grant)	-0-	41,058 (261)	41,058 (261)	-0-
National Library of Canada, Ottawa.				
Production of CONSER/COM.	-0-	23,000	23,000	-0-
The New York Public Library, New York, on behalf of the National Citizens Emergency Committee to Save Our Public Libraries.				
Research on future role of public libraries in preparation for White House Conference on Library and Information Services (\$15,000—1978)	15,000	-0-	14,579	421
OCLC, Inc., Columbus, Ohio.				
Development of non-Roman alphabet capability for library processes	-0-	15,000	15,000	-0-

	Unpaid 6/30/78	FY 1979		Unpaid 6/30/79
		Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	
Organization of American States, Washington, D.C.				
Travel and report production costs of meeting to approve MARCAL (\$12,000—1976)	\$ 6,525	\$ (5,682)	\$ 843	-0-
Princeton University, Princeton, N.J.				
Microform service development (\$10,000—1976)	8,750	(3,160)	5,590	-0-
Carl M. Spaulding, Sunnyvale, Calif.				
Travel grant to chair meetings of new standards group, the Library Committee of National Micro- graphics Association	-0-	2,000	442	1,558
State Univ. of N.Y. at Binghamton.				
Meeting on retrospective collection development	-0-	2,675	-0-	2,675
Stockton State College, Pomona, N.J.				
Innovative use of <i>Books for College Libraries II</i> (\$5,150—1977)	3,150	-0-	3,150	-0-
Syracuse University, Syracuse, N.Y.				
Improved subject access to books by augmentation of MARC records (\$76,615—1976; \$6,958—1977)	6,573	(2,515)	4,058	-0-
University of California, Berkeley.				
National shelflist measurement project (\$20,000—1978)	5,000	-0-	-0-	5,000
University of California, Los Angeles.				
Third edition of <i>Handbook of Data Processing for Libraries</i>	-0-	14,500	2,500	12,000
University of Connecticut, Storrs.				
New England Academic Librarians' Writing Seminar (\$20,610—1976)	9,943	-0-	7,017	2,926
University of Kentucky, Lexington.				
Preparation of "Leaders in American Academic Librarian- ship, 1925-75"	-0-	10,000	-0-	10,000

	Unpaid 6/30/78	FY 1979		Unpaid 6/30/79
		Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	
University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill.				
Administration of ANSI Committee Z-39 Through June 1978 (\$23,719— 1976)	\$ 11,219	\$ (1,194)	\$ 10,025	\$ -0-
Totals	916,128	500,808 (106,282)	595,445 (2,192)	717,401
	<u>\$916,128</u>	<u>\$394,526</u>	<u>\$593,253</u>	<u>\$717,401</u>

Schedule of Appropriations for Council-Administered Projects (unaudited)

June 30, 1979

	Appropriated Balance 6/30/78	Appropriations (Restored to Funds)	Awards (Restored to Appropriations)	Project Costs Paid	Appropriated Balance 6/30/79
Academic Library Development Program 1977-78	\$ 89,210	\$ (87,704)		\$ 1,506	-0-
Academic Library Management Intern Program 1977-78	358	(120)	\$ 234	4	-0-
Continuation 1978-79	6,026	(3,270)		2,756	-0-
Continuation 1979-80	94,520	(25,000)	58,000	6,658	\$ 4,862
Continuation 1980-81		135,000		2,099	132,901
College Library Program	39,382	1,676	41,058		-0-
Committee for the Coordination of National Bibliographic Control	4,879	1,500		6,379	-0-
Committee on book paper and preservation		8,000 (3,994)		6	4,000
Computer output microfilm study	528	(528)			-0-
CONSER project	6,425		(12,223)	426	18,222
Fellowship Program 1978-79	2,468	(1,599)	868	1	-0-
Continuation 1979-80	59,539	(33,622)	23,569	2,348	-0-
Meetings of LC's Network Advisory Committee and its Network Technical Architecture Group	22,075	(14,660)		7,415	-0-
Plan for a National Periodicals Center		4,854		4,854	-0-
Travel (foreign) by U.S. librarians for purposes important to profession	1,081				1,081
Travel (other) by U.S. librarians for purposes important to profession	953				953
Travel (U.S.) by foreign librarians	<u>2,200</u>				<u>2,200</u>
Totals	<u>329,644</u>	<u>151,030</u> <u>(170,497)</u>	<u>123,729</u> <u>(12,223)</u>	<u>34,452</u>	<u>164,219</u>
	<u>\$329,644</u>	<u>\$ (19,467)</u>	<u>\$111,506</u>	<u>\$34,452</u>	<u>\$164,219</u>

Council on Library Resources, Inc.

Opinion of Independent Accountants

August 9, 1979

To the Board of Directors of
Council on Library Resources, Inc.

We have examined the balance sheet of the Council on Library Resources, Inc. (Council) as of June 30, 1979, and the related statements of revenues, expenses and changes in fund balance, and of changes in cash and short-term investments for the year then ended. Our examination was made in accordance with generally accepted auditing standards and accordingly included such tests of the accounting records and such other auditing procedures as we considered necessary in the circumstances.

In our opinion, the financial statements examined by us present fairly the financial position of the Council on Library Resources, Inc. at June 30, 1979, and the results of its operations and the changes in its cash and short-term investments for the year then ended, in conformity with generally accepted accounting principles consistently applied.

Our examination was made primarily for the purpose of forming our opinion on the financial statements, taken as a whole. We also examined the Supplementary Statement of Revenues, Expenses and Changes in Fund Balances, by similar procedures. In our opinion, this supplementary information is stated fairly in all material respects in relation to the financial statements, taken as a whole. Although not essential for a fair presentation of financial position, results of operations and changes in cash and short-term investments, this information is submitted as additional data.

Price Waterhouse & Co.
Washington, D.C.

Council on Library Resources, Inc.

Balance Sheet

June 30, 1979

Assets

Cash and short-term investments	\$1,555,995
Grants receivable (Note 2)	6,537,024
Prepaid expenses and deposits	4,285
Accrued royalties	<u>740</u>
Total assets	<u>\$8,098,044</u>

Liabilities and Fund Balance

Accounts payable and accrued employee benefits	\$	30,586
Grants and fellowships payable		717,401
Federal excise taxes payable		1,834
Deferred income (Note 2)		<u>6,704,292</u>
Total liabilities		<u>7,454,113</u>
Unrestricted fund balance		
Appropriated	\$164,219	
Unappropriated	<u>479,712</u>	<u>643,931</u>
Total liabilities and fund balance		<u>\$8,098,044</u>

Council on Library Resources, Inc.

Statement of Revenues, Expenses, and Changes in Fund Balance

For the Year Ended June 30, 1979

	<u>Unrestricted</u>	<u>Restricted</u>	<u>Total</u>
Revenues (Note 2)			
Grants and contracts	\$700,000	\$321,359	\$1,021,359
Investment income	89,936		89,936
Royalty income	<u>1,754</u>	<u> </u>	<u>1,754</u>
Total revenues	<u>791,690</u>	<u>321,359</u>	<u>1,113,049</u>
Expenses (Notes 2 and 3)			
Program services	461,876	321,359	783,235
Administrative services	<u>223,981</u>	<u> </u>	<u>223,981</u>
Total expenses	<u>685,857</u>	<u>321,359</u>	<u>1,007,216</u>
Excess of revenues over expenses	105,833		105,833
Fund balance, beginning of year	<u>538,098</u>	<u> </u>	<u>538,098</u>
Fund balance, end of year	<u>\$643,931</u>	<u>\$ </u>	<u>\$ 643,931</u>

Council on Library Resources, Inc.

Statement of Changes in Cash and Short-Term Investments

For the Year Ended June 30, 1979

Sources of cash and short-term investments

Excess of revenues over expenses from operations	\$ 105,833
Increase in deferred income	3,695,127
Increase in federal excise taxes, accounts payable and accrued employee benefits	<u>2,011</u>
	<u><u>\$3,802,971</u></u>

Uses of cash

Decrease in grants and fellowships payable	\$ 198,727
Increase in accrued royalties	187
Increase in grants receivable	2,657,522
Increase in prepaid expenses and deposits	<u>113</u>
	<u>2,856,549</u>
Increase in cash and short-term investments for the year	<u>946,422</u>
Cash and short-term investments, beginning of year	<u>609,573</u>
Cash and short-term investments, end of year	<u><u>\$1,555,995</u></u>

Notes to Financial Statements

June 30, 1979

1. *Organization*

The Council on Library Resources, Inc. (Council) is a non-profit organization incorporated under the laws of the District of Columbia in 1956 for the purpose of promoting library research. The Council's operations are financed primarily through two five-year unrestricted general support grants from The Ford Foundation and The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation and through several restricted grants and contracts from private foundations and other sources. The Council conducts its work through directly administered projects as well as grants to and contracts with other organizations or individuals.

The Council is a private operating foundation and is exempt from Federal income tax under Internal Revenue Code section 501(c)(3). It is, however, subject to a 2% excise tax on investment and royalty income under the provisions of the Revenue Act of 1978.

2. *Summary of Significant Accounting Policies*

The Council's financial statements are prepared on the accrual basis. Grants are recorded as receivable at such time as the Council is notified that it has been awarded the funds. Unrestricted grant revenue is recognized in accordance with the budgeted annual payments specified by the grantors. Grant, contract, and fellowship expenses relating to this unrestricted revenue are recorded when the recipients are notified that they are to receive the funds. Interest and royalty income are recognized as unrestricted grant revenue. Restricted grant revenue is recognized to the extent of the related expenses. All unrecognized grant revenue is recorded as deferred income.

The costs of office furniture and equipment are consistently charged to expense when incurred. The Council does not consider such expenditures to be sufficiently material to warrant capitalization and depreciation.

3. Functional Allocation of Expenses

The Council's costs of providing program and administrative services for the year ended June 30, 1979, are summarized in the schedule that follows.

	<u>Unrestricted</u>	<u>Restricted</u>	<u>Total</u>
Expenses			
Program services			
Grants, fellowships and contracts	\$ 319,709	\$181,099	\$ 500,808
Council-administered projects	34,452	140,260	174,712
Less adjustments resulting from excess allocations of grants and fellowships	(106,282)		(106,282)
Compensation and employee benefits	188,128		188,128
Other expenses	<u>25,869</u>		<u>25,869</u>
	<u>461,876</u>	<u>321,359</u>	<u>783,235</u>
Administrative services			
Compensation and employee benefits	110,892		110,892
Rent	39,330		39,330
Travel and meetings	16,601		16,601
Other	<u>57,158</u>		<u>57,158</u>
	<u>223,981</u>		<u>223,981</u>
Total expenses	<u>\$685,857</u>	<u>\$321,359</u>	<u>\$1,007,216</u>

4. Retirement Plan

Employees are eligible for participation in the Council's retirement annuity program, which is administered through the TIAA/CREF insurance companies. Individual contracts issued under the plan provide for full and immediate vesting of both the Council's and employees' contributions. The Council's contribution amounted to \$41,000 for fiscal year 1979.

5. Commitments

The Council is committed to a lease for office space expiring in 1982 which provides for minimum annual rentals of approximately \$41,000.

Council on Library Resources, Inc.

Supplementary Statement of Revenues, Expenses, and Changes in Fund Balances

For the Year Ended June 30, 1979

	Unrestricted				Restricted					
	Ford Foundation	Mellon Foundation	Other	Total	Bibliographic Service Program (Note 2)	Committee for the Coordination of National Bibliographic Control	National Library of Medicine	Plan for a National Periodicals Center	Total	Total
Revenues										
Grants and contracts	\$500,000	\$200,000		\$700,000	\$86,170	\$14,926	\$189,116	\$31,147	\$321,359	\$1,021,359
Investment income			\$ 89,936	89,936						89,936
Royalty income			1,754	1,754						1,754
Total revenues	<u>500,000</u>	<u>200,000</u>	<u>91,690</u>	<u>791,690</u>	<u>86,170</u>	<u>14,926</u>	<u>189,116</u>	<u>31,147</u>	<u>321,359</u>	<u>1,113,049</u>
Expenses (Note 1)										
Program services										
Grants, fellowships and contracts	235,011	70,198	14,500	319,709	10,618		170,481		181,099	500,808
Council-administered projects	26,528	7,924		34,452	75,552	14,926	18,635	31,147	140,260	174,712
Less adjustments resulting from excess allocations of grants and fellowships	(81,837)	(24,445)		(106,282)						(106,282)
Compensation and employee benefits	144,859	43,269		188,128						188,128
Professional fees	5,030	1,502		6,532						6,532
Travel and meetings	6,682	1,996		8,678						8,678
Other expenses	8,207	2,452		10,659						10,659
	<u>344,480</u>	<u>102,896</u>	<u>14,500</u>	<u>461,876</u>	<u>86,170</u>	<u>14,926</u>	<u>189,116</u>	<u>31,147</u>	<u>321,359</u>	<u>783,235</u>
Administrative services										
Compensation and employee benefits	85,387	25,505		110,892						110,892
Travel and meetings	12,783	3,818		16,601						16,601
Professional fees	5,756	1,719		7,475						7,475
Rent	30,284	9,046		39,330						39,330
Equipment rental and furniture	9,014	2,693		11,707						11,707
Printing	8,316	2,484		10,800						10,800
Office and other expenses	19,513	5,829	1,834	27,176						27,176
	<u>171,053</u>	<u>51,094</u>	<u>1,834</u>	<u>223,981</u>						<u>223,981</u>
Total expenses	<u>515,533</u>	<u>153,990</u>	<u>16,334</u>	<u>685,857</u>	<u>86,170</u>	<u>14,926</u>	<u>189,116</u>	<u>31,147</u>	<u>321,359</u>	<u>1,007,216</u>
Excess of revenues over expenses	(15,533)	46,010	75,356	105,833						105,833
Fund balances, beginning of year	418,122	80,392	39,584	538,098						538,098
Fund balances, end of year	<u>\$402,589</u>	<u>\$126,402</u>	<u>\$114,940</u>	<u>\$643,931</u>	<u>\$</u>	<u>\$</u>	<u>\$</u>	<u>\$</u>	<u>\$</u>	<u>\$ 643,931</u>

See accompanying notes to Supplementary Statement of Revenues, Expenses, and Changes in Fund Balances.

Council on Library Resources, Inc.

Notes to Supplementary Statement of Revenues, Expenses and Changes in Fund Balances

For the Year Ended June 30, 1979

1. Allocation of Expenses

Under the terms of the Ford and Mellon foundations' unrestricted general support grants, the Council must account for expenditures of these funds on an individual basis. The Council allocates these expenses between the Ford and Mellon grants based upon the ratio of the sums of the respective fund balances at the beginning of the year and current year's revenue. Unrestricted expenses related to investment and royalty income are excluded from the Ford and Mellon allocation process.

2. Bibliographic Service Development Program

During 1978 and 1979, the Council was awarded restricted grants totalling \$4,400,000 from the following sources: the Carnegie Corporation of New York, The Commonwealth Fund, The Ford Foundation, The William and Flora Hewlett Foundation, the Lilly Endowment, Inc., The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, the National Endowment for the Humanities and the Alfred P. Sloan Foundation. The purpose of these grants is to fund a five-year research and development project to assist in establishing primary components of a national bibliographic system. The Council currently estimates the costs of this project to be \$6,100,000. Additional funding from various sources will be sought as the project progresses.

Index

- Academic Library Management
Intern Program 25–26
- Academic Library Program
19–20, 21
- American Library Association 24, 28
- American National Standards
Committee Z39 16–17
- Anglo-American Cataloging Rules* 15
- ARL Office of Management Studies
19–20
- Association of Research Libraries 19
- Bibliographic Service Development
Program 14–16, 17–18
- Books for College Libraries* 24
- British Library Resources* 28
- Carnegie Corporation of New York
7, 20
- CLR Fellowship Program 26–27
- College Library Program 20–21
- Committee for the Coordination of
National Bibliographic Control 16
- Commonwealth Fund 7
- CONSER project 17–18
- Council of National Library and
Information Associations, Inc. 17
- Downs, Robert B. 28
- Educational Resources Information
Center 16
- Exxon Education Foundation 7
- Ford Foundation 7
- Franklin and Marshall College 21
- Handbook of Data Processing for
Libraries* 18
- Hayes, Robert M. 18
- Health Sciences Library Manage-
ment Intern Program 26
- Hewlett (William and Flora)
Foundation 7
- IFLA International Office for
UBC 19
- International Federation of
Library Associations and
Institutions 15, 19, 21–22
- International Standard Biblio-
graphic Descriptions 19
- Joint Committee on Bibliographic
Standards 15
- Lake Forest College 20
- Library of Congress 7, 15, 17,
18, 23, 24
- Lilly Endowment 7, 20
- Mellon (Andrew W.) Foundation
7, 20, 22, 23
- National Citizens Emergency
Committee to Save Our Public
Libraries 29
- National Commission on
Libraries and Information
Science 7, 16, 17, 23
- National Endowment for the
Humanities 7, 14, 16, 20
- National Library of Canada 17
- National Library of Medicine 7, 15
- National Periodicals Center 23
- National Science Foundation 16, 17
- National Shelflist Measurement
Project 24
- Network Advisory Committee 14–15
- Network Development Office 15–16
- OCLC, Inc. 17, 18
- Princeton University 22
- Sloan (Alfred P.) Foundation 7
- Stockton State College 24
- Tusculum College 20
- U.S. Office of Education 17
- Universal bibliographic control
18–19
- University of California, Berkeley 24
- Wiegand, Wayne A. 29
- Xerox Corporation 22

Program Guidelines

The Council on Library Resources, Inc. is a private operating foundation. Established in 1956 by the Ford Foundation, the Council continues to receive support from it as well as other foundations. Over the years the Council has sought to be of assistance to those who are concerned with the quality of library operations and the character of library service. Through research, development, demonstration, and dissemination of results, CLR seeks to reduce obstacles that hamper those who need and seek information.

How CLR Works

The Council awards grants to individuals and organizations for projects that fall within CLR program interests and hold promise of meeting stated goals. The Council's present concerns, which are fully discussed in the chapter "Program Highlights," include:

- bibliographic services
- library resources and their preservation
- library operations and services
- professional education and training

Proposals are reviewed internally in accordance with established procedures. In addition, the Council frequently involves consultants in the evaluation of proposals on a confidential basis.

As an operating foundation, the Council also initiates and administers a limited number of specific programs. Occasionally, the Council enters into contractual arrangements.

CLR acts as a catalyst, often bringing together the expertise of many people and organizations for a mutual exploration of a major issue. It is a coordinating agency, organizing participation in certain cooperative undertakings. Finally, it provides consultation services when

requested in areas where help is needed but funding is either not sought or not possible.

What Will Not Be Funded

No foundation can support all the legitimate needs of libraries. From the beginning the Council has established a policy of not providing support for certain categories of activity in order to concentrate on programs where funding is either limited or nonexistent. Thus CLR does not entertain proposals for building construction or improvement, purchase of collections or equipment, or normal staffing or operational costs. Because the Council attempts to support programs that will result in benefits to many libraries, grants are not provided for programs that will be useful only to the institutions in which they take place.

Application Procedures

Initial inquiries regarding possible project support should be in the form of a letter, which should include the following information:

1. Name and address of requestor and of proposed principal investigator, if it differs.
2. Type of institution.
3. Tax status.
4. A clear statement of the aims of the project, its significance, the general approach and specific research methods to be used.
5. Amount of request and proposed budget.
6. Period to be covered by project.

If a proposal is judged to be of possible interest, advice will be offered as to proposal preparation and additional information may be requested. All inquiries should be addressed to Warren J. Haas, President, Council on Library Resources, 1 Dupont Circle, Suite 620, Washington, D.C. 20036.

